

Synthesis of Possible Amoebacides. Part VIII

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Syntheses of β - and α -(3-alkyl-4-methoxyphenyl)ethylamines with alkyl substituents as butylⁿ and amylⁿ are described.

Based on the high *in vitro* amoebacidal activity of β - and α -(2-hexylⁿ-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)ethylamines^{1,2}, Sawhney and Kachru³ prepared a few β - and α -(3-alkyl-4-methoxyphenyl)ethylamines having alkyl substituents as Me, Et, and Prⁿ as potential amoebacides. In this communication the syntheses of the Buⁿ and amylⁿ analogues are described. These amines have been tested for amoebacidal activity, the results of which will be reported elsewhere.

o-Butyl- and *o*-amyl-phenols, prepared according to the procedure adapted by Scaulesco and Girard⁴, were methylated in the usual way with dimethyl sulphate and alkali. The corresponding *o*-alkylanisoles were subjected to Gattermann's aldehyde synthesis, as modified by Adams and Levin⁵, to yield 3-alkyl-4-methoxybenzaldehydes. Appropriate β -nitrostyrenes have been prepared according to the procedure of Lange and Hamburger⁶. The nitrostyrenes, however, did not solidify and consequently their ethereal extracts were directly reduced with lithium aluminium hydride to yield the corresponding β -(3-alkyl-4-methoxyphenyl)ethylamines.

α -(3-Alkyl-4-methoxyphenyl)ethylamines were obtained by reduction with sodium and ethanol of the ketoximes derived from the corresponding ketones, prepared by the Friedel-Crafts condensation of appropriate *o*-alkylanisoles with acetyl chloride in carbon disulphide solution.

EXPERIMENTAL†

3-Butylⁿ-4-methoxybenzaldehyde.—Dry hydrogen chloride was bubbled through a mixture of *o*-butylanisole (33 g.), zinc cyanide (50 g.), and anhydrous benzene (100 ml) at 0° for an hour. Powdered anhydrous AlCl₃ (40 g.) was added to the mixture and HCl

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† All the melting and boiling points are uncorrected.

1. Kachru and Pathak, this *Journal*, 1957, **34**, 611, 768.

2. Kaushiva, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1957, **10C**, 224.

3. This *Journal*, 1956, **36**, 121, 466.

4. *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1930, **47**, 1300.

5. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **45**, 2373.

6. *Ibid.*, 1931, **53**, 3965.

passed for further 3 hours at 0°, then at 30° for 1 hour, and finally for 2 hours at 50°. Next day, the mass was decomposed by ice and HCl. A buff-coloured semisolid mass separating was refluxed for 2 hours. The benzene layer was separated and the aqueous layer extracted twice with benzene. The combined benzene extracts were washed with water and dried over anhydrous CaCl₂. Benzene was removed and the residual oil distilled *in vacuo*; b.p. 130-35°/10mm, yield 5 g. (13%). Its *semicarbazone* crystallised from dilute ethanol, m.p. 124-25°. (Found: N, 16.6. C₁₃H₁₉O₂N₃ requires N, 16.8%). 2,4-DNP crystallised from dilute acetic acid, m.p. 182°.

3-Amyl¹-4-methoxybenzaldehyde.—B.p. 165°/10mm, yield 15%. 2,4-DNP was crystallised from dilute acetic acid, m.p. 159°. The *semicarbazone* was crystallised from dilute ethanol, m.p. 128°. (Found: N, 15.8. C₁₄H₂₁O₂N₃ requires N, 15.9%).

β-(3-Butyl¹-4-methoxyphenyl)ethylamine.—A mixture of 3-butyl¹-4-methoxybenzaldehyde (2.88 g.), nitromethane (0.91 g.), and methanol (4 ml) was cooled to 5°. To this solution was added slowly with constant stirring a methanolic solution of NaOH (1.25 g. in 6 ml), previously cooled to 5°. The addition was completed in 10 minutes and the temperature was not allowed to rise above 15°. After an hour, ice-cold water was added to dissolve the precipitated solid and this solution was poured with stirring into a beaker containing HCl (1:1). The nitrostyrene separated as a semisolid mass which did not solidify. The aqueous layer was decanted and the yellow viscous oil was extracted with ether. The ethereal layer after drying over anhydrous CaCl₂ was subjected as such to reduction with LiAlH₄.

The ethereal solution of the above nitrostyrene was added dropwise during 2 hours to a well-stirred solution of LiAlH₄ (1.5 g.) in anhydrous ether (200 ml). The mixture was then slowly warmed to a gentle reflux. After cooling, the excess of LiAlH₄ was decomposed with water, the mixture filtered, and ether-extracted. The ethereal layer after separation was dried over solid KOH and to it HCl gas was passed, when the *amine hydrochloride* separated as a white solid. It was crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 168°. (Found: N, 5.8. C₁₃H₂₂ONCl requires N, 5.7%).

β-(3-Amyl¹-4-methoxyphenyl)ethylamine.—The amine was converted into the *picrate* which was crystallised from dilute ethanol. It decomposed at 160°. (Found: N, 12.38. C₂₀H₂₆O₂N₄ requires N, 12.44%).

3-Butyl¹-4-methoxyacetophenone.—Powdered anhydrous AlCl₃ (35 g.) was gradually added to the well-cooled solution of acetyl chloride (15 g.) in CS₂ (150 ml) and after an hour *o*-butyl¹ anisole (25 g.) was slowly added with constant stirring and cooling in ice-water. After keeping overnight, the mixture was warmed on a steam bath for half an hour. CS₂ was distilled and the residue decomposed by powdered ice. The product was extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was successively washed with water, 10% NaOH solution, and water and later dried over anhydrous CaCl₂. Ether was removed by distillation and the residual liquid distilled *in vacuo*; b.p. 175-78°/14mm, yield 7g. (22%). Its *semicarbazone* was crystallised from dilute ethanol, m.p. 174°. (Found: N, 15.7. C₁₄H₂₁O₂N₃ requires N, 15.9%).

3-Amyl¹-4-methoxyacetophenone.—B.p. 185-87°/15 mm, yield 39%. The *semicarbazone* was crystallised from dilute ethanol, m.p. 170°. (Found: N, 15.23. C₁₅H₂₃O₂N₃ requires N, 15.16%).

α -(3-Butylⁿ-4-methoxyphenyl)ethylamine.—The preceding ketone (5.5 g.), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (3 g.), and sodium acetate (6 g.) were dissolved in minimum amount of ethanol and the solution was refluxed on a water bath for an hour. On cooling and diluting with water, an oil separated which did not solidify. It was extracted with ether and dried over anhydrous CaCl_2 . Ether was removed and the residual crude oxime was reduced as follows.

To the hot solution of the crude oxime in 'super dry' ethanol (100 ml) metallic sodium (10 g.) was added rapidly to maintain a vigorous reaction. After all the sodium had dissolved, the reaction mixture was cooled. The solution was acidified with HCl (conc.) and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The residual mass was extracted with benzene to remove any unchanged reactants. The acidic layer on keeping deposited a white crystalline solid, identified as the *amine hydrochloride*. It was crystallised from a mixture of absolute ethanol and ethyl acetate, m.p. 197° , yield 2 g. (31% based on the ketone). (Found: N, 5.7. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{22}\text{ONCl}$ requires N, 5.7%). The *amine picrate* was crystallised from dilute ethanol, m.p. $151-52^\circ$.

α -(3-Amylⁿ-4-methoxyphenyl)ethylamine.—B.p. $140-44^\circ/10$ mm. It was converted into the *hydrochloride*, which was crystallised from a mixture of ethyl acetate and absolute ethanol, m.p. 156° , yield 25% (on the basis of the ketone). (Found: N, 5.52. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{24}\text{ONCl}$ requires N, 5.43%). The *amine picrate* was crystallised from dilute ethanol, m.p. $149-50^\circ$.

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